

Polong Renten: in Improving the Welfare of Employees of Village Owned Business Institutions (Bumdes) in Lombok Utara Regency

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ABSTRACT: BUMDes development in North Lombok Regency is accelerating; practically all communities in North Lombok Regency now have BUMDes. Along with its development, BUMDes in the North Lombok district is experiencing a number of issues within the BUMDES institution itself, including concerns with its accreditation. (1) Each BUMDes performance has not been optimized; (2) A lack of a conducive business climate; (3) a lack of information and market access; (4) a lack of capital; and (5) a lack of entrepreneurial spirit and spirit among employees, all of which have an impact on the performance and welfare of BUMDes personnel. In order to improve BUMDes performance in North Lombok Regency. What must be done is to strengthen the importance of social capital. Until date, there has been a significant social capital in North Lombok Regency; the social capital in question is the rent-seeking system. Polong Renteng serve as recommendations for the community in terms of behavior, respecting one another among people, implementing a mutual cooperative living, and contributing to the people's lives in North Lombok Regency. If all organizational managers follow this advice, the organization's performance will improve.

A literature review was chosen as the research method in this study. The findings revealed that the social capital of Polong Renteng played a significant influence in boosting the performance and welfare of BUMDes employees in the North Lombok district. This component of rent-seeking pod social capital serves as the social glue that holds the group together. With this broader component, the quality and quantity of BUMDes organizations/institutions (performance) can be improved, hence improving the welfare of BUMDes management. Furthermore, the existence of BUMDes in villages in the North Lombok region is often seen as successful and seamless since it has had a good impact on local communities. Implications for the development sector and community empowerment, particularly in building business abilities, boosting knowledge, skills, and attitudes that will lead to increased revenue. The establishment of BUMDes is capable of growing and nurturing an entrepreneurial spirit in rural communities, as well as instilling a sense of responsibility for policy.

KEYWORDS: Polong Renteng, Social Capital, Performance, Welfare of BUMDes Employees

I. INTRODUCTION

Inequality in welfare between areas is a classic development problem that persists in Indonesia. People's welfare can be judged by their health, economic situation, happiness, and quality of life (Segel and Bruzy, 1998:8). Welfare is a goal that people strive for in their life. If poverty can be reduced, general welfare or people's welfare can be raised, hence boosting general welfare can be accomplished through poverty reduction activities. The issue of poverty and economic disparity, both between groups and between regions (rural and urban), is a topic worth debating.

North Lombok Regency is one of the regencies in the West Nusa Tenggara province. North Lombok Regency's location is very strategic, as it is located in the golden triangle area as a tourism destination, while the sea transportation route with the Lombok Strait as a sea transportation route is becoming increasingly crowded, from the Middle East for fuel oil traffic and from Australia in the form of metallic minerals to the Asia Pacific. There are also a number of small islands in North Lombok Regency that are well-known for their natural beaches, including Gili (island), Gili Air, Gili Meno, Gili Trawangan, and other small islands. North Lombok Regency, for example, has considerable potential in the agricultural sector of food growing, producing rice, corn, cassava, sweet potatoes, peanuts, and green beans. Cashew, coffee, cloves, vanilla, cocoa, and coconut are examples of plantations. Considering the natural circumstances owned by North Lombok Regency, which are suitable for development, it is

Polong Renten: in Improving the Welfare of Employees of Village Owned Business Institutions (Bumdes) in Lombok Utara Regency

not consistent with the degree of wellbeing of the people in North Lombok Regency, which has the lowest level of community welfare in West Nusa Tenggara Province.

Overcoming difficulties requires the government's aid in accelerating economic development in order to result in the village economy achieving independence or sovereignty (sustainable strengthening). According to Kalla (2011) and Arifin (2001), any rural development or agricultural improvement effort will be difficult to implement and may even fail. This is mostly because the traditional sector has a low level of capital ownership (land or other land) (rural or agriculture). The most critical aspect of rural-urban relations is to maximize the utilization of local economic resources and to prioritize economic operations. This is precisely what needs to be done in every community in the North Lombok district. Villages can be formed through increasing economic activity with a high added value, for example, by establishing economic associations (institutions).

Until now, rural economic institutions have played a critical role in and contributed to efforts to achieve village economic independence. To advance the community's welfare, the village may establish a corporate organization known as BUMDes. BUMDes' aim should be to manage and maximize the town's resources. This village-owned business entity is one formed/established by the village administration, with the village government and the community co-owning and managing the capital. According to Wiwik Utami's research (2019), BUMDes is a social community with a singular goal, as articulated in its vision and mission, of enhancing rural communities' welfare through productive activities that are aligned with the area's economic potential and values. BUMDes' management has been inadequate due to a lack of knowledge and a scarcity of human resources interested in working for and managing BUMDes. According to Hasan Sidik (2020), BUMDes can contribute significantly to village economic development by boosting branding and marketing reach for the products produced.

The Villages Law No. 6 of 2014 and Permendagri No. 39 of 2010 provide a legal framework for BUMDES to operate as economic actors that collaborate to manage village potential for the benefit of villagers. BUMDES is a financial institution whose aim is to enhance rural communities' well-being. This indicates that BUMDES, as one of the village developments pillars, is expected to produce an independent village capable of managing its own household independently of the central government's village fund budget. According to Suriadi (2019), BUMDes was formed to develop local resources, specifically through leveraging village communities that are BUMDes members to participate in the future development of BUMDes.

BUMDes development in North Lombok Regency has been rather rapid; virtually all communities in North Lombok Regency now have BUMDes. In 2019, 25 BUMDes were detected in 33 villages in North Lombok Regency, with 22 being active, three being inactive, and the other eight villages being BUMDes-free. The 25 present BUMDes were dormant for several months following the natural disaster of the 2018 earthquake in West Nusa Tenggara, which resulted in the economy collapsing, particularly in North Lombok Regency, which was the hardest hit. North Lombok Regency's economy steadily improved, allowing for gradual resolution of this issue. Only 22 of the existing 25 BUMDes are operational again. The decentralized governance is expected to maximize the potentials of the people of North Lombok Regency in order to rebuild the economy.

The North Lombok Regency Government announced on its official website that it will convert each subdistrict's BUMDes program into a BUMDes Mart. Naturally, several parties have endorsed this magnificent initiative aimed at economic development in each hamlet. However, the North Lombok Regency Government's magnificent proposal has not been fully implemented. There are still numerous challenges inside the BUMDes institution, including (1) each BUMDes' performance has not been optimized. (2) An unfavorable business climate; (3) Inadequate information and market access; (4) Scarce funds; and (5) Employees' lack of entrepreneurial spirit, which has an effect on the BUMDes' performance.

Overcoming obstacles that arise above and beyond the critical role of the government in regulating measures aimed at improving BUMDes performance in North Lombok Regency. According to a 2016 study by Valentine Queen Chintary, the government's involvement in institutional management is the primary unit of development for the community. According to Sofyani (2019), the factors that contribute to BUMDes performance are the employees' patriotism and enthusiasm, their skills, training, education level, experience, honesty (ethical behavior), a sense of responsibility, sincerity, seriousness, concern for the environment and community, tenacity, teamwork, open communication between BUMDes managers, an unyielding attitude toward achieving performance targets, religiosity, and job satisfaction. According to study conducted by Moh. Hudi Setyo bakti (2017), the context of creating BUMDes is expected to be a driving factor for economic villages, which implies that the development of BUMDes must be able to provide villagers with both economic and social benefits.

Performance indicators are crucial for increasing business profits, which is ultimately distributed to employees or BUMDes managers. Performance refers to the accomplishment of an activity, program, or policy in achieving the organization's goals, objectives, mission, and vision. Strategic planning for an organization entails establishing a set of objectives that must be attained. In general, performance refers to an accomplishment made by a business over a specified time period. (2013)

Polong Renten: in Improving the Welfare of Employees of Village Owned Business Institutions (BUMDes) in Lombok Utara Regency

(Kurniawan, Muhammad, 2013: 5) BUMDes ' performance may be summarized as follows: it can provide excellent service to the community; it can accommodate various government initiatives; and it can improve living standards through BUMDes.

Recently, BUMDes ' performance in North Lombok Regency has substantially improved, as seen by the expansion of BUMDes into BUMDes Mart in six sub-districts and the expansion of BUMDes into Anyar Village, which now has three BUMDES business units. To begin, it collaborates with microfinance institutions, most notably BUMDes LKM. We have already generated a 6 billion rupiah profit. Second, the local government established BUMDes Mart in 2015, growing its revenue from Rp. 93 million in 2015 to Rp. 500 million in 2018. Additionally, in 2020, Bumdes constructed the Pertamina Desa Pert-shop in collaboration with PT. Pertamina, which we intend to convert into one of the BUMDes business units in Anyar. However, BUMDes' success in Anyar Village is unique compared to that of other BUMDes.

To enhance BUMDes performance in the North Lombok Regency, what needs to be done is to emphasize the critical nature of social capital. Dewi Kirowati (2018) discusses the role of social capital in the management of village-owned enterprises (BUMDes) in her research, stating that trust, the network in the form of renten responsibility, and norms that are represented in supporting one another have been well implemented in managing BUMDes. According to Wulandari's (2020) research, substantial social capital ownership is a marker of a stable, familiar, and compact society. This condition will have an effect on the network's size and the flow of information or ideas necessary to promote business performance growth. All of these behaviors are definitely voluntary and motivated by a shared goal of success. Numerous previous studies, including those conducted by Firdaus (2018), Rusydi Syahra (2003), Sugiyanto (2017), Handoyo (2013), Hadisurya (2013), Fatimah (2018), Ahmad Subaki (2011), Gandhiadi (2018), Wijaksono (2010), Oka Warmana (2018), and Ahmad (2019), have concluded that it is critical for managers or employees to leverage social capital in order to improve an organization's or company's performance and thus Similarly, there is significant social capital in North Lombok Regency up to this point; the social capital in question is the polong renten. Renten system formed by the people of North Lombok Regency. North Lombok Regency's inhabitants are quite diversified, belonging to a variety of tribes and religions. Despite the town's high concentration of religious adherents, social life appears to be cordial, and there have never been conflicts or confrontations between religious followers.

Polong renten is a term that alludes to the familial ties that exist among religious congregations in North Lombok Regency. Windi Maretha (2015) discovered that the Polong renten kinship system operates as a unifying force among religious believers in North Lombok Regency, acting as a spirit in carrying out community activities that incorporate interfaith community components. Polong renten serves as a model for the community in terms of how to behave, how to respect one another, how to live in mutual cooperation, and how to assist the lives of people in North Lombok Regency. The North Lombok people's harmony mantra is Mepolong Merenten. Both expressions are colloquial for "brothers." Renten is the eastern term for "brother," whereas pod is the western term for "brother." The populace is convinced that they all share a fraternal bond. Mepolong Merenten is a phrase used by the inhabitants of North Lombok to convey feelings of respect and fraternity (Suyadi: 2019).

In rural settlements in North Lombok Regency, social capital is extremely robust and deeply ingrained (Polong renten). One sort of social capital in question might be described as the village community's diverse social connections and strong social solidarity, which serve as an essential buffer for government, development, and community activities. The health of rural communities' social capital, on the other hand, remains inversely proportional to the level of village economic capital, with rural communities' social capital comprised of social bonds, social bridges, and social networks. To create a socially vibrant village within the framework of local democracy, the village community becomes parochial or superficial, and thus incapable of assisting economic development (Harmiati. 2017).

It is reasonable to assert that Polong renten's social capital has an effect on the performance and well-being of BUMDes staff in North Lombok Regency. Citta Cendani (2015), Dewi Kirowati (2018), Aji Ratna Kusuma et al. (2013), Robiatul Adawiyah (2018), Ahmad Subak et al. (2011), Fajar Sidik (2015), Marco Hadisurya (2017), Rika Fatimah (2018), World Bank (1998) in Syahyuti (2008), Devi Analia (2019), Santoso (2019), Suriadi (2017), World Bank (1998) in The proposed understanding is predicated on the following assumptions: (a) social capital is related to economics, social and political relations, and social relations influence how markets and the state operate; (b) stable relationships between actors can promote the effectiveness and efficiency of both collective and individual behavior; and (c) social capital in a society can be strengthened but requires certain conditions.

It emphasizes the social capital that results from group cooperation in the Polong renten system, which is connected to traditional policies such as honesty, maintaining commitment to complete tasks consistently, engaging, communicating, and cooperating regardless of religion, color, or ethnic origin. This simplifies the process for all BUMDes employees and managers

Polong Renten: in Improving the Welfare of Employees of Village Owned Business Institutions (BUMDes) in Lombok Utara Regency

who collaborate, interact, and foster a comfortable, harmonious work environment that contributes to BUMDes performance, which in turn contributes to the company's revenue and employee welfare in North Lombok Regency.

Based on a variety of theoretical and argumentative issues, as well as interesting facts such as the one above, a strategy is required to maintain the existence of Polong renten social capital in the lives of social communities in North Lombok district, which will have an effect on the working environment within the organization, particularly BUMDes, thereby increasing performance and improving the welfare of BUMDes employees. This is demonstrated by the social capital components that promote the quality and quantity of BUMDes institutions/organizations with an impact on BUMDes management. BUMDes' performance is determined by their management. The operation of BUMDes is crucial in developing a better village through the effective use of community social capital. This study sought to determine the relationship between Polong renten's social capital, performance, and employee welfare at BUMDes. The analysis used a literature review methodology to determine the relationship between Polong renten's social capital, performance, and the wellbeing of BUMDes employees.

II. METHOD

In this study, the research approach was decided to be a literature review. The goal of this study was to see if Polong Renteng's social capital had a substantial impact on the performance and well-being of BUMDes employees in the North Lombok district. The findings of this study are based on a number of theoretical foundations and empirical studies from earlier research.

III. DISCUSSION

A. Social Capital of Polong Renten

North Lombok Regency is one of the regencies in the province of West Nusa Tenggara. North Lombok Regency's location is extremely advantageous, as it is located in the golden triangle area as a tourism destination, while the sea transportation route via the Lombok Strait is becoming increasingly congested, with traffic from the Middle East for fuel oil and from Australia for metallic minerals to the Asia Pacific. Additionally, there are other tiny islands in North Lombok Regency that are well-known for their natural beaches, including Gili (island), Gili Air, Gili Meno, and Gili Trawangan. For example, North Lombok Regency has substantial agricultural potential, producing rice, corn, cassava, sweet potatoes, peanuts, and green beans. Plantations include cashew, coffee, cloves, vanilla, cocoa, and coconut. It is inconsistent with the level of welfare enjoyed by the residents of North Lombok Regency, despite the fact that the natural environment in North Lombok Regency is suitable for improvement.

We're discussing Polong renten. This is comparable to the concept of civil service culture or the attitude toward mentoring younger generations by elder folks. Polong renten translates as "we are all brothers," which suggests that if an issue arises, it may be resolved appropriately or by discourse, and the family culture

is stronger. <http://www.rmol.co/read/2012/12/07/88818/Budaya-Polong-Renten-Mampu-Atasi-Konflik-di-Lombok-Utara->

Polong renten, according to Windi (2015), is employed as a kinship relationship that unites all villages in the Regency. North Lombok, which does not consider the community's tribe, religion, or ethnicity. Because the population of North Lombok Regency is made up of different social strata, both in terms of religion and ethnicity. As a result, polong renten is being utilized as a binder for everyone in Bayan District, Kab. North Lombok.

Mepolong Merenten, which means "brotherhood" in Indonesian, emerged from the fact that this region has adhered to three religions since time immemorial, namely Islam, Hinduism, and Buddhism. With this concept, we as the next generation can experience what is known as inter-religious fraternity, which is bound by a slogan, namely Mepolong Merenten (brothers). The inhabitants of North Lombok frequently utilize this terminology to demonstrate respect and brotherhood to others. Whether consciously or unconsciously, the term Mepolong Merenten can convey pleasant recommendations to anyone. In this context, the "Mepolong Merenten" familial tradition must serve as a constructive, instructive, and transparent communication instrument, free of mutual suspicion and rationalization. Suyadi (2019:91). The formation of the state emblem in "Bhineka Tunggal Ika," which was re-initiated by the nation's founding fathers after independence, is the solution to what is happening now in the archipelago. Many communal organizations in this country prefer to use violence to settle disputes rather than promote brotherly principles.

A quick look back on the island of Lombok, particularly in North Lombok, reveals that what our parents did from the start was absolutely correct. They regard the ideas of brotherhood embodied in "Mepolong Merenten" as one of the most essential mediating tools for the conflicting parties' peace (related to violence, fights, inheritance, and household problems and so on). Although this is acknowledged, not all legal disputes may be settled amicably. Especially in our modern period, when people's attitudes have been influenced by a variety of factors (technology, information, attitude patterns, life needs and others). From a

Polong Renten: in Improving the Welfare of Employees of Village Owned Business Institutions (BUMdes) in Lombok Utara Regency

cultural standpoint, the people of North Lombok, for example, have the same tendency in solving community problems, whether they are problems between individuals or problems involving many people, one of which is through family deliberations, which are usually facilitated by traditional leaders, village heads, to Pemusunan (Village Head). It is not uncommon for the word "Mempolong Merenten" to be the breaker of existing difficulties throughout the mediation process. In the context of Pilkada, "Mempolong Merenten" is meant to chill or neutralize the situation. Usually, the fury of two people involved in a conflict dissipates after they realize they are basically linked in the connection of "Posting Merenten."

Individuals in North Lombok also use the phrase Mempolong Merenten as a beginning sentence in any engagement with new people they meet. Like mbe elek pe enten? (Where are you from?), sai aran pe pods? (What is your name?), and a variety of other greetings. It is unclear when the inhabitants of Dayan Gunung popularized this uniting vocabulary, but it is evident that the term "Mempolong Merenten" was known to the people of North Lombok long before the country gained independence. "Mempolong Merenten" not only has the value of unity and harmony, but it also has a social spirit that may break down social barriers. When a person feels like a Dayan Gunung person, regardless of ethnicity, color, or religion, he enters the kinship line that is tied by the word "Mempolong Merenten." The people of North Lombok have been known as a humble people since ancient times. The emotional bond that has been formed among the Dayan Gunung people has served as the foundation for the development of a strong kinship system. (Suyadi.2019:91).

So, based on some of the answers in this paper, the social capital in question is the Polong renten system, which is used by the community to live a life that is always harmonious, peaceful, mutual aid, mutual respect, and strong brotherhood values. Polong renten refers to the family relationships that exist between religious communities in North Lombok Regency. Polong renten acts as a guide for the community in how to behave, respect each other among people, and implement a mutual cooperation life. Please assist in the lives of the people in North Lombok Regency.

B. The role of Polong Renten social capital in improving the performance of BUMDes and the welfare of BUMDes employees in North Lombok Regency

According to Theo Suhardi's (2014: 100) Performance Theory, performance is heavily influenced by each individual's ability, motivation, excitement, and expectations for a person, group, and company. Similarly, in increasing the performance of BUMDes in the North Lombok area, beginning with Polong renten's social capital, which is manifested through mutual trust and cooperation to achieve common interests and build new networks. Polong renten's social capital generates new resources and motivates all BUMDes management to work even harder in expanding BUMDes institutions, which is one of BUMDes's performances.

BUMDes managers with social capital will be dedicated to moving the village forward through BUMDes. Through collaboration between BUMDes administration and the community, social capital also generates social partnership and economic empowerment for BUMDes development. Not only that, but social capital may be used to help and promote villages through effective cooperation and symbiosis between BUMDes administration and village government.

The social capital of Polong renten is social capital as a kinship bond between religious congregations and in the lives of people in North Lombok Regency. Polong renten acts as a guide for the community in how to behave, respect each other among people, implement a mutual cooperation living, and support people in North Lombok Regency's lives. This guideline is still utilized as a reference by existing BUMDes managers so that BUMDes activities can be carried out more efficiently, and the performance of existing BUMDes will improve over time. The improved performance has an effect on the well-being of its employees.

According to Andreas Suranto's (2019) research, there is a link between social capital and BUMDe performance. The basic component of social capital, which consists of networks, norms, and social beliefs, and a larger component that adjusts to the environmental, cultural, and socioeconomic conditions of a community, are both visible. The presence of this social capital component undoubtedly has an impact on BUMDes management. Individual factors such as socioeconomics, age, human capital (education and occupation), income, and gender all have an impact on BUMDe management. These variables give rise to existing actors in BUMDes, who subsequently create social capital elements to increase power and interests. The emergence of these BUMDes actors demonstrates the strategy's efficacy in achieving common interests in BUMDes. This is BUMDes' performance in developing BUMDes' potential. Similarly, Subakti (2018) asserts that the role of groups, the role of vertical networks, the role of networks, the role of norms, the role of integration, and the role of vertical trust all influence organizational performance, financing performance, and performance, as well as the impact felt by organizational members. These are networks of social capital. As a result, social capital can be said to have an impact on an organization's performance.

Polong Renten: in Improving the Welfare of Employees of Village Owned Business Institutions (Bumdes) in Lombok Utara Regency

Several more studies, including those conducted by Devi Analia (2019) and Djoko Santoso (2019), have found that, in addition to natural capital, physical capital, and human capital, capital is one of the success elements of micro and small companies (UMK). Social networking site (network). The network (network) has an impact on the performance of micro and small businesses (UMK). A micro network is a network that is established between business actors and customers (consumers), whereas a meso network is a relationship built by actors with and or in the group. This meso network can also be evident in people' relationships with government entities that facilitate the existence of micro and small businesses (UMK).

As a result, Polong renten's social capital can be stated to play an essential role in boosting the performance and welfare of BUMDes employees in the North Lombok district. The desire of BUMDes managers and communities to make the component of Polong renten social capital used to strengthen groups or individuals on BUMDes performance.

Figure 1 depicts the descriptive model of the association between Polong renten's Social Capital and the Performance and Welfare of BUMDes Employees in North Lombok Regency.

The study of Polong renten's social capital in the management of BUMDes is manifested in the current component of Polong renten 's social capital, which is a guide for the community in North Lombok district in behaving, as shown in Figure 1. The social capital components of Polong renten are networks, norms, and trust. It can be implemented into a larger component through the major component of Polong renten 's social capital. Of course, this broader component is tailored to the environmental, cultural, and socioeconomic requirements of each village in the North Lombok area. According to Coleman's 1988 thesis (Hauberer, 2011), the main notion introduced is that social capital is a resource inherent in social ties. Individuals in social interactions can use these social resources to further their personal and communal goals.

Figure 1. Descriptive model of the relationship of Polong renten 's Social Capital to the Performance and Welfare of BUMDes Employees in North Lombok Regency (Processed)

This social capital component serves as the social glue that holds the community together. With this broader component, the quality and quantity of BUMDes organizations/institutions (performance) can be improved, hence improving the welfare of BUMDes management. It is vital to test the relationship and communication between members of the BUMDes organization/institution in order to sustain mutual harmony. This test tool takes the shape of social capital aspects. These components of social capital are related to the quality and quantity of BUMDes organizations/institutions, and thus have an impact on BUMDes management.

C. The implication of BUMDes is on the growth of village development in North Lombok Regency.

The village is a sub-system of governance in the region, so the village government is the most important entity in serving the community and serves as a strategic point. Several factors influence the village's independence, including decentralization of

Polong Renten: in Improving the Welfare of Employees of Village Owned Business Institutions (Bumdes) in Lombok Utara Regency

authority, the capacity of the apparatus (HR), financial strengthening, changes in village government institutions and community institutions, and empowerment of the village community itself, which can be seen from various perspectives (Manig, 1992).

Development work to boost the village economy will eventually be able to increase community independence and relieve poverty. Progress in the economic sector, which is the focal point of development, has a link or continuity that begins with the central government and continues with the backing of a favorable economic climate at the provincial level. The solid economy at the district level influences economic progress at the province level. Meanwhile, progress at the district level is aided by a strong rural economy. The rural economy is inextricably linked to societal well-being.

Until now, rural economic institutions have been both an important part of and a source of weakness in efforts to achieve village economic independence. According to Widjaja (2014: 76), the aims of delegating affairs to the regions include: developing the region in numerous domains, boosting community services, increasing regional independence, and increasing regional competitiveness in the growth process. Village Original Income is one of the fundamental capitals used by the village authority to carry out development and satisfy village expenses. Village Original Income is a village attempt to reduce reliance on the government. In order to properly execute autonomy, the village must have its own robust finances in addition to the Village Fund Allocation (ADD). The bigger the village's funds, the higher the village's ability to deliver communal services.

The function of the Village Government is critically needed in order to raise Village Original Income (PADes) by optimizing village potential by leveraging various types of village potentials that are owned through the development and administration of Village Owned Enterprises. Village-Owned Enterprises (BUMDes) are economic enterprises run entirely by the community. The purpose of BUMDes should be to manage and utilize all resources, as well as to push the economy in rural areas that have historically lagged behind their metropolitan counterparts (Ramadana, 2013).

The Presence of Villages Law No. 6 of 2014 offers a legal framework for BUMDes as economic players who cooperatively manage village potential to benefit the welfare of villagers. BUMDes is a financial institution that works to improve the well-being of rural communities. This means that BUMDes, as one of the village development pillars, are supposed to establish an autonomous village that is confident and successful in managing its own home, so that the village does not rely solely on the village fund budget provided by the central government.

Looking at the existence of BUMDes in the North Lombok district, it is clear that the continuing improvement in the performance of existing BUMDes has a good impact on village economic growth in the North Lombok district. Village-owned enterprises (BUMDes) have a role in providing services to village communities, particularly in the commercial sector. According to Kusuma Dewa's (2014) research, the possibility for democratization at the village level should also have a good impact on the village's ability to establish initiatives and desire to improve the village. The project must include various factors, including services, democratization, and participation, but the most crucial factor is enhancing the village's economic potential. Improving the village economy should begin with establishing the necessary legal framework so that BUMDes can truly demonstrate its role in increasing Village Original Income (PADes) and growing the village economy as a whole and completely.

Alfirdausi also proposed another investigation (2019) that the establishment of BUMDes is extremely useful to the community, as evidenced by the many programs offered by the village to the community, such as reducing unemployment and assisting persons who wish to become entrepreneurs. The formation of BUMDES in the North Lombok area is a representation of the village community's overall participation, therefore it does not create a business model that is dominated by specific groups at the village level. This suggests that the implemented regulations are robust institutional processes. Building institutional capability will result in the establishment of rules that bind all members. The existence of BUMDES is projected to boost development, which will have an impact on increasing the welfare of rural areas, which will eventually become national welfare.

The establishment of BUMDes in North Lombok Regency is a learning process, which means that the presence of BUMDes in each village in North Lombok Regency can have an impact on increasing community capacity, both individually and collectively, which not only adapts to change, but also directs it so that it serves its own purpose. BUMDes village development is concerned not only with the objectives to be attained, but also with improving the capability of its human resources. The community can acquire and practice their abilities in BUMDes management by encouraging the community to establish BUMDes and putting them in charge of the BUMDes. Furthermore, the community must be able to process and use existing BUMDes. As a result of the learning process, the village community has been able to establish new enterprises and earn more money, allowing them to enhance their standard of living.

Polong Renten: in Improving the Welfare of Employees of Village Owned Business Institutions (Bumdes) in Lombok Utara Regency

CONCLUSIONS

Some conclusions can be taken from the preceding discussion:

1. The social capital in question is the Polong renten system, which the community uses to live a life that is constantly harmonious, peaceful, assisting each other, respecting each other, and based on strong brotherhood ideals. Polong renten are kinship relationships amongst religious communities in North Lombok Regency. Polong renten serves as a guide for the community in how to behave, respect each other among people, and implement a mutual cooperation life, so please assist in the lives of people in North Lombok Regency.
2. The social capital of Polong renten is vital in increasing the performance and well-being of BUMDes personnel in the North Lombok district. This component of Polong renten 's social capital serves as the social glue that holds the community together. With this broader component, the quality and quantity of BUMDes organizations/institutions (performance) can be improved, hence improving the welfare of BUMDes management.
3. The existence of BUMDes in villages in the North Lombok region is often regarded as successful and seamless, owing to the good impact it has on rural communities. The consequences of BUMDes are related to community development and empowerment, particularly in building business skills, expanding knowledge, skills, and attitudes, all of which will have an impact on income growth. The establishment of BUMDes is capable of growing and nurturing an entrepreneurial spirit in rural communities, as well as instilling a sense of responsibility for policy.

SUGGESTION

1. For BUMDes managers, so that the social tradition of Polong renten is preserved in BUMDES management. Polong renten can have a good impact on BUMDes management by making it more effective and maximizing BUMDes performance in order to provide equal welfare for employees and the community.
2. For the village government to keep the Polong renten social capital tradition alive. Because Polong renten acts as a guide for the community in how to behave, respect each other among people, implement a mutual cooperative life, and assist people in their lives. If this is still used as a guide for the community, it will have an impact on many people's survival, which is even greater.
3. Please aid in people's lives for the local government, so that Polong renten's social capital can be utilized as a guideline for the entire community, especially the people of West Nusa Tenggara, in behaving, respecting each other among people, and implementing a mutual cooperation life.

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